

SCIENTIFIC AND HYDROGRAPHIC USE OF THE BATHYMETRIC SWATH SURVEY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The Bathymetric Swath Survey System (BSSS), in use on the NOAA Ship DAVIDSON, is an important mapping tool for both the scientific and hydrographic user. The 36 kHz system covers the sea floor in a swath of 21 beams, each 5 degrees wide, for a total swath width of 105 degrees. That is equivalent to 2 1/2 times the water depth being surveyed. It is designed for use in water depths up to 600 meters. By overlapping adjacent swaths, one can obtain complete survey coverage of key areas such as navigational corridors. An example is shown of BSSS data from a recent survey of the San Andreas Fault. The BSSS data from that survey were complemented by the simultaneous operation of a 3.5 kHz sub-bottom profiler and the ship's 100 kHz narrow beam echo sounder.

This paper will approach the subject of the remote sensing of sea floor bathymetry using the Bathymetric Swath Survey System (BSSS) from the viewpoint of scientific and hydrographic users. Descriptions of the system and its early testing have been covered in considerable detail by Hopkins and Mobley (1978), McCaffrey (1981), and Farr (1980). Recent test results which quantify the system's accuracy in various water depths have been presented by Pryor (1982 a,b).

The hydrographer surveys the sea floor to collect data in support of nautical charting. The emphasis is on precisely-positioned least depths, so that a navigator using a nautical chart can be reasonably certain that there is sufficient depth for the passage of his vessel. The depth on the nautical chart may be the least of hundreds or thousands of soundings taken in the original survey of the area. He takes some bottom samples to determine general sediment types. A marine geologist or other scientist usually is after a contoured bathymetric map that will show features such as faults, ridges, and valleys. The geologist is interested not only in sediment and rock type, but also the sub-bottom structure. While the hydrographer and the scientist differ in their emphasis and end products, their survey requirements are quite similar. The new swath

mapping systems such as the BSSS fulfill the needs of both users in the same survey, even though the data may be processed to emphasize different features for each user.

Before considering the mechanics and advantages of the swath mapping system, it is useful to see why it evolved. The echo sounders used prior to the 1960's sent out a wide sound cone on the order of 30 to 60 degrees wide. The wide cone covered a large area, but there were problems with slope corrections and hyperbolic echoes, as well as not knowing where under the cone the least depth was to be found. The answer was the narrow beam echo sounder, with a beam of about 2-10 degrees in width. One version of the Narrow Beam Echo Sounder used by the National Ocean Survey for deep sea surveying has a 2.7 degree stabilized beam. The narrow beams are excellent for providing the sharp return needed by digital echo sounders coupled to a computer. The problem with the narrow beam systems is that they only cover a small strip along the sea floor, leaving large unsurveyed areas between lines. Hopkins and Mobley (1978) point out that only 2-5 percent of the area "surveyed" is actually seen or measured during the course of the conventional hydrographic survey. Unless the waters are wire dragged, there is no assurance that something has not been missed between lines.

The answer to having wide coverage, but at the same time having a number of narrow beam readings across the swath of the coverage, is the multi-beam swath sounder. The BSSS uses 21 receiving beams, each five degrees wide and spaced on five degree centers (Figure 1). Actually there are 11 beams on both port and starboard sides, but the center beams overlap so that the total swath is 105 degrees wide. It covers swaths with a width of roughly 2.5 times the water depth. As in most wide angle remote sensing systems, the outer beams are subject to increasing errors as the distance to the sea floor increases. Consequently, the inner beams are designed for detailed surveying which meets hydrographic charting standards, while in deeper waters the outer beams are for slightly less accurate reconnaissance. Some of the outer beam errors may be due to uncompensated roll and sound speed errors, but much probably is related to pulse stretching of the returning signal (Angelari, 1978). The inner beams receive a relatively

Figure 1. BSSS beam pattern.

narrow pulse with straighter edges. The outer beam returning pulses are much more rounded and stretched, with the slope of the leading edge of the pulse decreasing as the pulse width increases. With a fixed detection threshold level, the pulse detection time will vary as the pulse stretches. The system can be programmed to reject low amplitude signals. Farr (1980) provides an excellent discussion of the decision algorithm used in processing the returning signals and points out that it has been designed to give good accuracy in shallow waters, but increasing errors in deeper waters. The BSSS is designed for use in waters ranging from ten to over 600 meters. While tests show that it will work in waters deeper than 600 meters, the accuracy of the soundings will degrade.

The BSSS has its own heave-roll-pitch sensor to correct the soundings for sea conditions. It also takes inputs from a gyrocompass, predicted or actual tides, sound velocity measurements, and four positioning system values. Normally, the positioning system used is Raydist, with calibration by Mini-Ranger. Although it could run on just Mini-Ranger, there is a need for a good smoothing routine to cut out bad range readings from the shore transponders. The data are fed to a Digital Equipment Corporation PDP 11/34 minicomputer and to magnetic tape to be logged.

The computer generates a real time position plot which includes swath width. It also generates a separate listing of vertical beam depths, with contours for those depths shoaler than the vertical soundings.

The BSSS, which is the only one of its kind, was developed for NOAA by the General Instrument Corporation. It is mounted aboard the NOAA Ship DAVIDSON, a 175-foot coastal research vessel (Figure 2). Since installation aboard the ship in 1978, some problems turned up in the hull-mounted transducer dome. In addition to modifications to the dome, a second set of transducers was mounted on fairings. Now both transducer arrays apparently are working well.

Figure 2. NOAA Ship DAVIDSON

During the Spring of 1981, there were a series of tests off Washington and Oregon to determine the accuracy of the system for hydrographic reconnaissance and detailed surveying (Pryor 1982 a, b). The results showed that in relatively shallow 30 meter deep waters over a hard bottom the soundings met international hydrographic standards for all beams. Similar tests over a soft bottom did not meet those standards for all readings. Deep water tests, conducted in over 600 meters, showed that the central 14 beams could be used to meet international standards, with the outer beams useable for reconnaissance. The shallow water results were compared against the ship's 100 kHz Ross Laboratories Fineline echo sounder with a 7.5 degree beam width, while the deep water tests were compared with the ship's 12 kHz Raytheon sounder with a 35 degree beam width. A large wreck showed up well in the shallow water tests, although as one might expect, a 60 centimeter triplane target moored 3.7 meters above the bottom was missed.

With the engineering testing of the system completed, in the summer of 1981 there was a hydrographic survey run using the BSSS in Shelikof Strait, Alaska. The survey was run in an area that already had been surveyed by another vessel

which used the more conventional Ross echo sounder. Water depths were approximately 120 fathoms. When the data were processed, it was found that the inner BSSS beams compared well with the other survey, but that the outer beams had enough divergent results to make the survey unacceptable by hydrographic standards. The problem apparently lies in computer programming which gives equal weight to a minimum reading from any beam, outer or inner. The post processing program divides the area into plottable unit areas whose size depends upon the scale of the output, then scans those areas for maximum and minimum soundings. Work is now underway on revised programming which will allow certain beams to be processed for the detailed hydrographic survey, with the outer beams used for reconnaissance to spot any large hydrographic features, obstructions, or wrecks. Preliminary results show that when the survey is reprocessed without the outer beam data and with a rejection of low amplitude readings, the results compare much more favorably to the prior survey.

With the results of the Alaskan survey in mind, there was a BSSS survey of the San Andreas Fault on the continental shelf off the coast of northern California during the Spring of 1982 (Figure 3). This was largely for scientific purposes in connection with crustal motion studies. The feasibility of such a survey already had been shown in a brief survey of the same area in 1979. A 3.5 kHz Ocean Research Equipment sub-bottom profiler was towed behind the ship in order to confirm the presence of the fault in the upper 100 meters of sediment. The fault tends to parallel the coastline between Point Arena and Tolo Bank. A series of zig-zag lines were run first to pinpoint the location of the fault. These were controlled by Loran-C, Mini-Ranger, and Raydist when it was available. In some places, the fault has a scarp 10-20 meters high, or it has been eroded out along the head of a canyon. A typical crossing at an oblique angle is shown in Figure 4, with simultaneous outputs presented for the 36 kHz real-time BSSS contour plot, the 100 kHz Ross record, and the 3.5 kHz O.R.E. sub-bottom profile. Note the steeply dipping beds shown in the 3.5 kHz profile.

The BSSS San Andreas Fault survey was run at a scale of 1:20,000, with a line spacing of approximately 1.5 times the water depth. Because the BSSS covers 2.5 times the water depth, there was an approximately 30% overlap of adjacent swaths. This permitted dropping out some of the outer beam data during processing. A sample of the processed data is shown in Figure 5, with machine-generated contours for the same area shown in Figure 6. Crosslines show good agreement with the main scheme of survey lines, which were run roughly parallel to the major trend of shelf contours. Data from the 100 kHz Ross echo sounder were recorded concurrently on the ship's HYDROPLOT system, although those data have not been processed. The BSSS and HYDROPLOT performed well during the survey, but there were problems with unusually poor weather and with the Raydist navigation system. Fortunately, those problems

Figure 3. Location of San Andreas Fault survey on portion of Chart 18620

did not severely impact the total survey because Loran-C could be used in reconnaissance lines to locate fault, and the weather had little adverse effect on the O.R.E. sub-bottom profiler fish, which was towed at a depth of 20 meters and which performed remarkably well. Once the weather and Raydist problems were solved, in 3 days the BSSS was used to completely cover the fault area in a 43 nautical mile long strip averaging about 1 1/2 nautical miles wide. The simultaneous data from the 36 kHz BSSS, the 100 kHz Ross and the 3.5 kHz O.R.E. sounding system gave an excellent definition of the fault (Figure 4). The results are very encouraging that the BSSS is a valuable scientific mapping tool, particularly when complemented by the other types of echo sounders.

It is interesting to compare the BSSS with its deep water cousin, the SEABEAM system aboard the NOAA Ship SURVEYOR. That system, also built by General Instrument Corporation, covers a swath approximately 73% of the water depth. It utilizes 16 receiving beams spaced at 2 and 2/3 degree

Figure 4. San Andreas Fault crossings on 36 kHz BSSS real time contour chart, 100 kHz echo sounder, and 3.5 kHz sub-bottom profile

intervals from 20 degrees port to 20 degrees starboard (Farr, 1980). From a user's viewpoint, the most significant difference is that SEABEAM produces a real time total contour chart of the swath, while BSSS contours only those depths shallower than the vertical beam. It would be very helpful if the BSSS could be modified to produce a totally contoured strip chart. The adjoining contoured strips can be placed together to produce an approximate contour map of the survey area without having to wait for post processing of the data.

Another feature of the SEABEAM installation aboard the SURVEYOR is a second offline computer to handle post processing. There are plans to put a second computer on the DAVIDSON for that purpose, thus allowing the construction of a boat sheet of the survey area at sea. It can be done at present, but the single computer can not be used for data acquisition while it is processing other data. The contouring programs required for covering a large area need a much larger computer than the PDP 11/34 minicomputer used by BSSS, but machine contouring at sea also is a worthwhile long range goal.

The future of BSSS as a hydrographic survey tool looks good, particularly in the light of trends toward the need for complete survey coverage in some areas. These include the need to assure completion of survey work in the assigned area while the vessel is still there, as well as the trend toward assessing user charges, coupled with the increasing cost of survey operations.

First, in the electronic era when soundings are inked by a plotter tied into a computer, rather than by hand, it is all too easy for "busts" in the data to escape attention in the field. It is possible to miss features, which may lie partially between survey lines, that should have been developed and checked out while the ship is in the survey area and costly electronic navigation control networks are still in place. Under the swath mapping approach of total sea floor coverage, however, all features would be covered and would show up on the real time contour strip chart, as well as on the boat sheet. If an indication of an interesting feature should be found in an examination of the data, it could be processed at a larger scale to bring out the details. If warranted, the appropriate features then could be developed and confirmed through conventional narrow beam surveys before the ship left the area.

There is a definite trend to let the user pay for Federal services and data through increased prices for products and through user fees. Presumably this could lead to a greater concentration of survey effort in those areas where the most users are able to pay the appropriate costs. That should lead to more detailed survey coverage in the more important economic zones, for the high cost of survey operations may preclude extensive survey operations in other areas. One example of the

need for detail would be in traffic lanes which have been set up on harbor approaches. Also, in at least 5 harbor approach areas, the Coast Guard has established vessel traffic service (VTS) areas where vessel movements are monitored by radio and radar, much as is done for aircraft on airport approaches. It follows that charted traffic lanes and zones of great economic importance on harbor approaches should receive complete survey coverage, something that becomes very feasible using the overlapping swath survey method. The same concept of total coverage could be useful in areas of military importance such as submarine transit zones, economically important mineral resource areas, or environmental hazard areas such as the San Andreas Fault.

In summary, the economic forces are such that we can expect a greater concentration of survey effort in special corridors and zones. The swath mapping concept fills this requirement very well, with the BSSS an excellent system for waters up to 600 meters deep. Once there is completion of the computer programming to improve the quality control of soundings to be used for charting vs. reconnaissance as a function of water depth and signal strength, the BSSS should be an excellent survey tool for both hydrographic and scientific purposes. This is especially true when it is complemented by the simultaneous operation of higher and lower frequency echo sounders. In such cases, one survey can fulfill the needs of several types of users.

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Figure 5. Sample of BSSS data output from San Andreas Fault survey. See data sample location on Figure 3

Figure 6. Sample of machine-contoured data from same area shown in Figure 5